

BRIEF EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF SCIENTIFIC WORKS ON DETERMINING NEUROTIC CONDITIONS IN MOTHERS

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Abstract : In methods research selected For empirical analysis studies conducted with mothers and children , we determined neurotic state personality , psychological features , anxiety and depression . For studying level mothers We used some methods research . In this article briefly reviewed analysis results obtained Heck and Hess " Test " For express diagnostics neuroses ."

Key words : neurosis , neurotic conditions , methodology , norm , diagnosis.

Method fast diagnostics neuroses by K. Heck and H. Hess (scale complaints BFB, K. Heck , H. Hess , 1975) was designed as screening questionnaire neuroses used For preliminary diagnostics before inspection doctor and also public epidemiological research used in investigations [5] . At creation techniques authors oriented on what complaints patients in neurotic condition wear specific character and unlike from patients with organic , somatic pathology prevail vegetative illnesses and mental complaints . Original version techniques includes list of 63 symptoms neurosis . To the point included somatic (disorder vision , double vision , seizures choking , tachycardia , complaints on heart and respiratory paths , tremor hands , etc.) and mental (violation speech , stuttering , difficulties communication , apathy , loneliness) fear , etc. given scroll complaints Answers test takers are interpreted quantitatively taking into account gender and age . Available three explanatory gradations results : " norm " , " probable" diagnosis neurosis " , " state neurosis ." Besides diagnostics possible neurotic state emotional index which Maybe indicate dominance psychosomatic or psychoneurotic diseases . Authors give meaning this indicator at choice methods psychotherapy . Analysis complaints carried out taking into account the following factors : excessive vegetative excitability (sympathicotonia) , apathy , phobia , vagotonia , asthenia , increased sensitivity , sensorimotor disorders , schizoid reactions and fear . Methodology standardized For adults (from 16 to 60 years old). Questionnaire Very simple , with her with help duration survey is 5-10 minutes , " raw " points are calculated using key , and then " raw " points converted to standard using special scales

The original version of the technique is usually used in medicine. A simplified version of this technique is used in practical psychodiagnostics (for example, in the field of individual counseling). The questionnaire consists of 40

statements to which the subject must answer “yes” or “no.” When processing the results, the number of positive responses is taken into account, and if all the obtained indicators are more than 24, this suggests the presence of severe neurosis.

To carry out the technique, the following instructions are given: From the list of given statements, the test taker selects suitable answers. In this case, agreement with the answer is expressed as “yes”, and disagreement as “no”.

When analyzing the results of the express diagnosis of neuroses (BFB complaint scale) by K. Heck and H. Hess, affirmative and negative answers were given to 40 questions; when processing the results, the number of positive answers was taken into account. , and if all the obtained indicators are more than 24, then this suggests the presence of severe neurosis.

According to the results of the study, it was found that out of 334 subjects, 150 had a low neurosis index, 82 subjects had an average neurosis index, and 100 subjects had a high neurosis index (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Indicator of maternal neurotic state.

Using the above method for diagnosing pronounced neuroses, one can see the presence of neuroses and tendencies to neuroses in 55% of the subjects. This confirms the reliability of the results obtained when assessing the state of frequent nervousness in the mother according to the data presented in Fig. 2-3 studies.

Figure 1.

Question 1: Do you often get nervous?

Figure 3.

Graphic depiction of mothers' frequent nervousness.

In Question 1, we asked the mother to rate the state of frequent nervousness. It was found that in 64 subjects, frequent nervousness was rarely observed, in 117 subjects - sometimes, in 152 subjects - often (see Fig. 2). Therefore, most mothers tend to get nervous often. Also, a high assessment of the relationship with the child and the child in relation to him, that is, the chosen option, may not have mutual proportionality, which is the reason for our assessment that it is associated with an attempt to idealize the relationship. Because according to the results of this question, 269 people, that is, almost 80.5% of the subjects, said that they were prone to nervousness (see Fig. 3).

In conclusion, it should be noted that there are many reasons for the occurrence of neurotic conditions in mothers. As the scope of her roles in public life expands, motherhood becomes the most responsible role. Apart from being a mother, a woman has to fulfill a number of roles such as wife, housewife, daughter-in-law and so on. This, in turn, leads to physical exhaustion of the mother, health and mental problems. Non-compliance by some mothers with the rules of reproductive health, short intervals between children could be a factor in the occurrence of chronic diseases of various forms, including anemia, vitamin deficiency and other sexual-genital, therapeutic diseases. So, health problems, in turn, have a serious impact on the psyche and can be an incentive to evaluate a neurotic state as a destructive factor.

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